

TESTING AND NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF IMPACT-DAMAGED STRUCTURES

Peter Shyprykevich

FAA William J. Hughes Technical Center, AAR-450, Atlantic City International Airport, NJ 08405, USA

John S. Tomblin and K. Suresh Raju

*National Institute of Aviation Research, Wichita State University, 1845 Fairmount Ave.,
Wichita, KS 67260-0093, USA*

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INTRODUCTION

It is well established that impact damage in composite sandwich structures is a serious threat to maintaining structural integrity, particularly under compression loading. Industry response to this threat has been to inflict impact damage on a structure to the extent that the damage is barely visible and demonstrate by test that the structure can withstand ultimate static load and one lifetime of spectrum loads. This approach has several difficulties. The selection of impactor diameter can change the visibility characteristics dramatically. Small-diameter impacts will be much more visible than blunt impacts. The industry standard of using 1-inch-diameter impactors may not be conservative. The residual indentation produced by the damage can also spring back to become invisible. The visibility criterion results in many unnecessary repair actions during maintenance because the operator does not know the effect of the damage on strength but only knows that all visible damage must be repaired. The visibility criterion penalizes designs that are damage resistant, either through the use of tougher material or design configuration. For instance, thicker facesheets and heavier core densities would tend to force such designs to have ultimate load levels at very low strains. The latter practice can lead to heavy, but fortunately, safe designs.

To address the difficulties enumerated above, the Federal Aviation Administration has invested in a sizeable research program in characterization testing of impact-damaged sandwich structures. The research was spurred by the use of sandwich structure in small general aviation airplanes, where new certification approaches had to be developed and by the maintenance difficulties encountered by airlines companies on older commercial aircraft parts. The results of this research in the two areas of interest, testing and nondestructive evaluation, are discussed in this paper.

IMPACT DAMAGE IN SANDWICH PANELS

The damage states in sandwich panels can be broadly classified as material damage states and geometric damage states. The material damage states include facesheet damage, core damage, and facesheet-core interface disbonds. The geometric damage state in sandwich panels manifests as a residual indentation distribution around the point of impact. The various damage states may occur simultaneously with the relative proportions being dictated by the intrinsic and extrinsic variables. In this section, the damage states observed during the experimental program are enumerated.

The facesheet damage states may be comprised of facesheet delaminations, matrix cracking, and ply/facesheet fractures [1,2]. The initiation of facesheet damage was observed to be dependent on the impactor size (diameter). A limited number of sandwich panels ($[(90/45)_2/\text{CORE}]_S$) with fiberglass facesheets (Newport NB321/7781) and honeycomb cores (Plascore PN2-3/16-3.0; 0.75" thick) were

impacted to study the facesheet damage states in sandwich panels. The translucency of the fiberglass facesheets was exploited to observe the facesheet damage states, since the underlying core damage masked the facesheet damage during the through-transmission ultrasonic C-scan (TTU C-Scan) measurements [1-3]. The facesheet damage was observed to initiate in the form of delaminations between the plies adjacent to the facesheet-core interface and these delaminations occurred above the honeycomb cell walls [2]. A network of delaminations was observed at higher impact energy levels. The area over which delamination networks occurred was found to increase with impact energy up to the point when facesheet fracture was initiated. The typical delamination networks in sandwich panels impacted with a 3.00" diameter impactor are illustrated in fig. 1. It was observed that the damage area measured by the TTU C-Scan method was consistently higher than the area corresponding to the facesheet delaminations. This implies that in practice, facesheet damage may go undetected in the absence of a conspicuous facesheet fracture. Further, the presence of a layer of paint or a nontranslucent facesheet makes it difficult to detect these facesheet damage states.

Figure 1. Typical network of delaminations observed in $[(90/45)_2/\text{core}]_s$ sandwich panels with fiberglass facesheets and honeycomb cores impacted with 3.00" diameter impactor.

The core damage in honeycomb core sandwich panels was observed to be predominantly cell wall buckling, core crushing, and cell wall fracture. The incipient failure mode in all cases was observed to be cell wall buckling, which propagated across the planar dimensions of the panel. The damage metrics associated with the core damage in sandwich panels (honeycomb core) is illustrated in fig. 2. The TTU C-Scan method measures the planar damage size $2R_{\text{damage}}$ of the core reasonably well. The damaged core increases the impedance of the honeycomb core to the ultrasonic waves and, thus, can be detected. The through thickness distribution of the core damage may be characterized by the maximum crush depth of the core Δ_{CRUSH} . This damage metric is of particular importance in analytical models for predicting residual strength of impact-damaged sandwich panels. The damaged core within the crushed region will offer no reaction to the facesheet under subsequent in-plane loads until the indentation depth increases by Δ_{CRUSH} . The ratio of planar damage size ($2R_{\text{damage}}$) to the maximum crush depth (Δ_{CRUSH}) will, in general, depend on the impactor size, facesheet stiffness, and the transverse compressive behavior of the core.

Figure 2. Core damage and associated damage metrics for honeycomb core sandwich panels.

DAMAGE RESISTANCE AND DAMAGE TOLERANCE TESTING

The damage resistance and damage tolerance of sandwich structures was investigated using three sandwich layup configurations, $[(0/45)_n/\text{CORE}/(45/0)_n]$, where $n=1, 2,$ and 3 . The facesheet material used in this study was Newport NB321/3K70 plain weave carbon fabric/epoxy prepreg. Plascore[®] Nomex honeycomb core of density 3.0 lb/ft^3 was used for the sandwich core. Several sandwich specimens with the aforementioned layup schedules with core thicknesses of $0.375''$ and $0.75''$ were fabricated using an autoclave cure cycle [4]. Test specimens were impacted using $1''$ and $3''$ diameter spherical steel impactors with various impact energy levels, using a drop-weight impact -testing machine designed and assembled at Wichita State University. The impact tests were conducted with a nominal impact velocity of 96.6 in/sec . The test specimens were clamped along four orthogonal edges, leaving a test area of $8'' \times 8''$. The sandwich specimens were subjected to nondestructive inspection to characterize and quantify the impact damage. The damage metrics used during this study are the planar damage area obtained using TTU C-scans and the maximum residual indentation depth. The relative magnitudes of the planar damage size and the maximum residual indentation were dependent on the impactor diameter. The relative magnitudes of the planar damage area and the maximum residual indentation depth for all the specimens tested in this program is shown in fig. 3(a). The $1''$ impactor produced small damage areas with conspicuous residual indentation. The residual indentation was often accompanied by visible matrix cracks, and the facesheet fractured at relatively low-impact energy levels. The $3''$ impactor produced large damage areas accompanied by very shallow indentation regions that were hard to detect visually. The energy levels required to produce facesheet cracks/fractures were considerably higher compared to that of the $1''$ impactor. It is evident from fig. 3 that the large subsurface damage states in sandwich panels impacted by a $3''$ impactor may go undetected when the inspection is based on the residual indentation depth criterion.

The damage tolerance of the impact-damaged sandwich panels were evaluated by conducting compression-after-impact (CAI) tests. The residual strength and failure modes of the sandwich panels under in-plane compressive loads were governed by the relative distribution of facesheet and core damage states. The impact damage due to smaller impactor produced a stress concentration-governed compressive failure of the facesheet across the width of the sandwich panel with the crack originating from the damage zone and propagating towards the lateral edges. The impact damage due to the larger impactor promoted a local buckling-initiated failure of the impacted facesheet. The residual strengths that corresponded to the compressive failure of the sandwich panels were consistently higher than the buckling-initiated failure.

The normalized residual strengths (ratio of residual strength of the impact-damaged panel to that of an undamaged panel) of sandwich panels impacted with $1''$ and $3''$ diameter impactors are plotted as a

function of planar damage area in fig. 3(b). The data is scattered around a hypothetical degradation curve irrespective of the impactor diameter. However, the data points that correspond to the smaller diameter impactor are spread over the initial portion of the curve while those for the larger impactor fall over the asymptotic region of the curve. The impact damage states in practice will only undergo a posteriori analysis based on the damage metrics, without any knowledge of the associated impact energies. The maximum residual indentation has been typically used as a measure of the severity of impact damage. The threshold of detectability based on the residual indentation is known as Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID). There is no consensus on a standard value for the BVID, even though it has been assumed that the strength degradation is proportional to the residual indentation depth. It has been shown in a previous study [3] that the maximum residual indentation depth does not necessarily correlate well with the CAI strength. Fig. 3(a) shows that large planar damage areas can exist while the maximum residual indentation is on the order of a few ply thicknesses (0.008" in this case). Thus, it was concluded that BVID is not a reliable indicator of impact damage; rather, the planar damage size better reflects the residual strength degradation in sandwich panels. In light of this observation, it becomes necessary to identify damage detection techniques and their effectiveness to quantify the planar damage size.

Figure 3. (a) Relative magnitudes of planar damage area to the maximum indentation depth in impacted sandwich panels and (b) the normalized CAI strength as a function of planar damage area.

NONDESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION (NDI) OF IMPACT DAMAGE USING FIELD TECHNIQUES

Because the implementation of an effective damage tolerance program dictates continual monitoring of airframe structures in service, it is desirable to use NDI methods, which would enable in situ delineation of damage states in sandwich airframe structures. Even though the TTU C-scan method is very reliable and accurate in detecting the core damage region, its portability and need to access both sides of the sandwich structure restricts its use on airframes in service. Thus, inspection techniques that are easily portable are better suited for field inspection of airframe structures. Some of the inspection techniques are the manual tap test (coin tap test), automated (instrumented) tap hammer [5], mechanical impedance analysis (MIA), etc. In this investigation, the effectiveness of different field inspection techniques (FITs) was appraised by comparing the damage size predicted by these techniques with that of the TTU C-scan (the damage size measured by TTU C-scan was found to correlate well with the underlying core damage [3]). The details of the TTU C-Scan equipment, calibration standards, and damage quantification procedures can be found in [3]. The FITs used in the study were manual impact tap hammer, the instrumented tap tester, and the mechanical impedance analysis and are briefly described in the following paragraphs.

Tap testing can be classified into mechanical tap testing and acoustical tap testing. Mechanical tap testing involves the analysis of the mechanical response of the structure subjected to a localized excitation. The acoustical tap test relies on the analysis of the characteristic resonant sound emanating from the location of the tap. The localized excitation in both cases is typically provided by a light impact using a spherical-nosed impactor, with energy levels low enough to preclude any damage during the inspection itself. In the present investigation, Mitsui Woodpecker automated tap tester [6], shown in fig. 4(a), was used to identify the impact damage in a sandwich panel using mechanical tap testing, while the manual tap test hammer (Airbus design), shown in fig. 4(b), was used for acoustical tap testing.

Figure 4. (a) Mitsui Woodpecker automated tap tester and (b) manual tap test hammer (Airbus design).

In this method, the stiffness of the structure in contact with a probe tip is measured. The mechanical impedance of the structure is a function of the constitutive properties of the sandwich components. This method has been popularly used for identifying flaws in adhesive bonds. The presence of facesheet or core damage will reduce the mechanical impedance of the sandwich structure and can result in a phase or amplitude change to the displayed signal, depending on the frequency of the probe. The probe consists of two piezoelectric crystals with the driver positioned behind the receiver within the same holder. The driver converts electrical energy into sonic vibrations and the receiver, in direct contact with the test surface, converts the modified vibrations into electrical signals for processing by the instrument. The V-95 low-frequency bond tester used in the present study is illustrated in fig. 5.

Figure 5. V-95 bond tester used for mechanical impedance analysis.

The effectiveness of using the aforementioned FITs for detection and quantification of impact damage in honeycomb core sandwich panels was investigated for different sandwich configurations. The honeycomb core sandwich panels used in this program belong to the design of experiments test matrix that was used to develop response surfaces for the impact resistance and damage tolerance of sandwich structures [7]. The material systems used for honeycomb core sandwich panels are summarized below.

Facesheet Material System	Newport NB321/3K70P plain-weave carbon prepreg
Layup Schedules	$[(90/45)/CORE]_s$, $[(90/45)_2/CORE]_s$, $[(90/45)_3/CORE]_s$
Core Types	Plascore Nomex Honeycomb PN2-3/16-3.0 PN2-3/16-4.5 PN2-3/16-6.0
Nominal Core Densities (lb/ft³)	3.0, 4.5, and 6.0
Adhesive	Hysol 9628.060 PSF NW film adhesive

The various sandwich configurations were impacted with impactor diameters of 1.00", 2.00", and 3.00" with different impact energy levels. The honeycomb sandwich panels were then subjected to non-destructive inspection using TTU C-Scan to obtain the planar damage diameter $(2R_{\text{damage}})_{\text{C-Scan}}$. The maximum residual indentation depth was also measured for all the sandwich configurations. The sandwich panels were then inspected using the FITs discussed previously. In each case, the center of impact was identified by a cross mark around which the inspections were conducted. The inspection locations were along horizontal and vertical lines passing through the center of impact and along lines at 45° to the horizontal and vertical lines. A network of grids spanning 4" × 4", (see figures 5 to 7) centered about the point of impact, was drawn on each specimen. The points along the boundary of the damaged region, as identified by the FITs equipment, were marked on a sheet of paper where a similar grid was drawn. The eight points along the boundary of the damaged region were then joined by a smooth curve to identify the damaged region. The average diameter of the damaged region was then computed relative to the grid to obtain the damage size.

Honeycomb Core Sandwich Panels

The effects of facesheet thickness on the detection capability of FITs were analyzed by comparing the average of all the normalized planar damage sizes for each facesheet type. The results are summarized

and plotted as a function of the number of (90/45) ply groups in the facesheets in fig.6. The error bars shown in the same figure correspond to one standard deviation about the respective mean value. From the figure, it can be seen that the FITs perform better with thinner facesheets. However, relatively higher scatter was observed for thinner facesheets. As the facesheets get thicker, the contribution of the core to the local stiffness (flexural) decreases, especially at the edge of the damage region. Thus, the facesheet tends to mask the core damage underneath, reducing the effectiveness of FITs, which rely on either the mechanical or the acoustical impedance of the sandwich panel. These trends are consistent with the observations of Georgeson, et al. [8] who used an electronic tap hammer for damage assessment.

Figure 6. Average normalized damage size for sandwich panels with different facesheet configurations (0.75" thick, 3.0 lb/ft³ cores).

Foam Core Sandwich Panels

Similar to the honeycomb core sandwich panels, the foam core sandwich panels were impacted with different combinations of impact energies and impactor diameters. Unlike the honeycomb core sandwich panels, a baseline damage size could not be obtained using TTU C-scan due to the high acoustical impedance of the foam cores. Therefore, one of the FITs was used as the baseline damage detection method. In this study, the V-95 bondcheck (MIA) method was used as the baseline method since it was the only method able to detect damage in all the specimens that were impacted. In addition to the FITs described for honeycomb core sandwich panels, MAUS C-scan was also used to detect damage in the foam core sandwich panels. This method, however, was used in the MIA mode rather than the through transmission (TT) mode and was used as verification for the V-95 bondcheck data.

The effects of facesheet thickness on the detection capability of FITs were analyzed by comparing the average of all the normalized planar damage sizes for each facesheet type. The results are summarized and plotted as a function of the number of (90/45) ply groups in the facesheets in fig.7. The error bars shown in the same figure correspond to one standard deviation about the respective mean value. Unlike in the case of honeycomb core sandwich panels, the Mitsui Woodpecker performs comparatively poorly

with respect to the manual (acoustic) tap tests, especially as the facesheet gets thicker. This implies that the acoustic impedance of foam core sandwich panels is relatively more sensitive to impact damage.

Figure 7. Average normalized damage size for sandwich panels with different facesheet configurations (0.75" thick, 2.6 lb/ft³ cores).

SIGNIFICANCE OF RESULTS

Impact damage in sandwich panels, which is caused by blunt impactors, has been found to lead to one of two contrasting final failure modes under in-plane compressive loads. The impact damage, which manifests in the form of a dimple, will be “active” well before the final failure occurs. The amount of this activity, which manifests itself in core failure as the dimple grows, will be dependent on the flexural properties of the facesheet, transverse compressive properties of the core, and the damage metrics. A thin facesheet with negligible flexural stiffness will promote a strain concentration adjacent to the impact damage and local compressive failure mechanism in the skin. This mechanism is dominant due to the instabilities of local skin damage and the inability of the thin skin to drive the dimple into progressive core failure. However, given enough flexural stiffness and local damage to the core, the facesheet will drive this dimple through a characteristic sequence of events leading to a stability-based failure mechanism.

The current investigations showed that tests with a range of impact energies and blunt impactors with different diameters (from 1" to 3") provided enough points to plot a CAI strength degradation curve. A typical CAI static strength degradation curve, as shown in fig. 8, provides knowledge of the CAI strength asymptote and its relationship to the static strength of the undamaged structure. Analysis and test efforts should evaluate the potential for specimen size effects on the shape and asymptote of the CAI strength degradation curve. Some evidence from this investigation suggests that the stability-based failure mechanism, which includes dimple growth, has some dependence on sandwich specimen size.

Figure 8. CAI static strength degradation curve.

Impact results from the current investigations indicated that the larger diameter impactor produced significantly different damage states when compared to the smaller impactor (at the same impact energy level) and that visual detection alone cannot be used to assess damage. The results indicated that the larger diameter impactor produced a very benign appearing damage state, where no surface fracture or cracks nor visually perceptible levels of indentation existed, but NDI did indicate a large damage region, which likely related to the observed reduction in strength. This damage scenario proved to be the most elusive when the impacted specimens were inspected using a typical visual inspection protocol. The results of these investigations show that the visual inspection methods are misleading and the residual indentation cannot be used as a reliable damage metric for static ultimate strength and damage tolerance criteria for sandwich structures. The results indicate the use of field inspection instruments are much more reliable at detecting overall damage to the sandwich structure.

Under the assumptions that additional field inspection techniques must be used to quantify the extent of damage in the structure, various field techniques for NDI were investigated. Based on the experimental results, it can be concluded that the detection of impact damage in honeycomb and foam core sandwich panels cannot be accomplished to the same level of accuracy using a single field inspection technique when compared to laboratory techniques. The experimental data suggests that the impact damage in honeycomb core sandwich panels is better detected by a technique which measures the local stiffness of the sandwich, while the damage in foam core panels can be best assessed with a technique relying on the measurement of acoustic impedance. The trends observed for foam core panels may be biased by the normalization procedure due to the inability to corroborate the damage size using destructive sectioning.

It was also observed that the reliability of detecting damage using field inspection techniques is generally reduced when compared to laboratory or manufacturing production C-scan methods. When the facesheet thickness increases, the ability of each field inspection technique to locate and characterize the extent of damage is reduced. It should also be noted that the maximum number of plies in this study was six fabric plies. For thicker facesheets, the measurement reliability will decrease. Thus, the measured damage in the laboratory may actually be two times greater than that measured in the field, which will likely influence the damage tolerance and inspection plans.

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